

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 3.6

Evaluation and Outcome Report on Ongoing Projects

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

MXX EJP SOIL project months
WP Work Package

1. Background

The EJP SOIL has had two internally funded research project calls: from the 1st call 10 projects were funded (D3.3) and they started on 1st of February 2021. From the 2nd call another 10 projects were funded (D3.5) and 9 have started on 1st of November 2021, and 1 project on 1st of December 2021. The projects are monitored and evaluated internally: the EJP SOIL WP3 has developed an evaluation and monitoring system (described in D3.1) in which the project coordinators submit reports to WP3 3 times per year. The reporting periods have been aligned to match the monitoring and evaluation periods of the EJP SOIL. At the time of submission of this deliverable 3.6 (M24) the 2nd call projects have not reported for a single time as they have been only running 2-3 months. The 1st call projects have been reporting earlier, although they (as well as the 2nd call projects) perform wider reporting only once per year, in February, as part of EJP SOIL annual reporting. The wider reporting that will be conducted in each February, and at the end of each project, will provide information for proper assessment of the projects (D3.1). In this deliverable 3.6, the milestones and deliverables of the internally funded research projects are listed and D3.6 will be updated with an evaluation of the projects once their annual technical reporting (M25) is submitted to WP3.

2. Evaluation and outcome of the EJP SOIL projects

2.1. EJP SOIL 1st internal call projects

For the first call, 8 topics were launched; 5 dedicated to research projects and 3 for synthesis/stocktaking activities. Topics launched for the projects related to Climate Change Mitigation (CM2, CM8), Soil restoration (SR5), Ecosystem services (ES7), and one Multi-topics (MT1). In relation to stocktaking and synthesis, the topics were related to Food security and Multi-topics (FS2/MT4), Ecosystem services (ES1/ES2), and Climate change adaptation (CA1).

Eleven proposals were submitted, 2 for CM2, 3 for CM8, 1 for SR5, 2 for MT1, and one proposal for each stocktaking or synthesis activity. No proposals were received for topic ES7. After the evaluation process, one of the CM8 proposals was rejected, and the total number of approved proposals was 10. The average number of partners by project was 10 (range 5 - 24 depending on the type), 23 in the stocktaking activities and 5 in the synthesis. The geographic coverage of the projects was good, fitting the call requirements, and the coordination was also distributed in different countries (Germany, Italy, Spain, Finland, France, Denmark, Austria, Netherlands and Belgium).

The projects' duration was 3 years for all but CM2 related topic (CarboSeq), which is a large project with 4 years of duration. The stocktaking and synthesis activities were planned for 1 year. The grant size was approximately 4 M€ for CM2 topic and between 1.1 -1.7 M€ for the rest of the projects. The stocktaking and synthesis activities were granted with 0.2 – 0.4 M€. This information is detailed in D3.3 "List of selected proposals of 1st internal call".

Additionally, in the D7.4 " Feedback to the Roadmap after Year 2", the scientific analysis of the first call's projects is addressed.

A summary of each project with the main results is presented as following.

CM2 – CarboSeq (project leader Thuenen, Germany)

Carbon sequestration in soils is a negative emission technology that can contribute to mitigate climate change. However, for European soils, a comprehensive assessment is missing on how much soil organic carbon (SOC) can be sequestered with different management options using also national data on agricultural management. The aim of CarboSeq is thus to estimate the feasible SOC sequestration potential taking into account technical and socio-economic constraints. The project will align with the current FAO activity for a global SOC-sequestration potential map (GSOCseq). The key for SOC-sequestration is an enhanced input of biomass (e.g. crop residues) to the soil. The final product of CarboSeq is the assessment of the European SOC-sequestration potential summarised in an interactive map for Europe. These SOC-sequestration potential maps for different management options will guide policy makers regional specific to the most efficient agricultural management options to sequester SOC for climate mitigation.

CarboSeq is approaching the end of the “data collection phase” that is crucial to estimate and update for each SOC sequestration measure their potential effect on SOC sequestration in different European pedo-climatic conditions. The data collection will serve as the basis to estimate and model the SOC sequestration potential of around 15 different options to increase SOC stocks in croplands and grasslands. The project also considers the subsoil as an overlooked C storage space, water locked mineral soils and also possible negative side effects with potentially increased N₂O emissions. Together with the potential area of implementation of the different management options, these data will be the key to a new consistent estimate of potential C sequestration to shape the role of SOC sequestration as negative emission technology in Europe. By the end of M24 (January 2022) almost 80% of the project tasks have started, the rest will start in the coming project years. All the deliverables and milestones planned for the 1st project year have been achieved in time (see the table below). The project is well on track and activities across all partners have started as planned.

Deliverable Milestone	/ Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1 Consortium agreement	M13	Feb 2021	YES	M13	
D1.2 Data platform	M13	Feb 2021	YES	M13	
D1.3 Website M15	M15	Apr 2021	YES	M15	
M01 WP1 Kick-off meeting	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	Successfully held as online meeting from 25th of February to 1st of March 2021.

M20 WP5 Questionnaire for data collection among CarboSeq partners and EJP	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	Together with EJP Soil Task 7.3 a joined questionnaire (“EJP SOIL template - Metadata Longterm field experiment (LTE)”) was developed in order to not overload partners and EJP site managers.
M27 WP8 Questionnaire on costs, benefits, and constraints of the SOCsequestration measures (WP2, 3, and 4)	M19	Aug 2021	YES	M19	A document has been sent to the steering committee and its results were discussed at the 3rd steering committee meeting on 22th September 2021.

CM8 - SOMMIT (project leader CREA, Italy)

The ΣOMMIT project will aim at understanding of soil management and its influence on climate mitigation. It will improve predictions of soil-environment-management interactions, providing indicators and model estimates of trade-offs at farm-level for the sustainable soil managements across relevant European climate zones. ΣOMMIT seeks for the effective stakeholder’s involvement. ΣOMMIT will deliver guidelines, built on co-learning approaches, resulting in practical tools for practitioners and decision makers.

ΣOMMIT will evaluate trade-offs and synergies between soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses as affected by soil management options aimed at increasing soil C storage. The integrated and interdisciplinary approach will address the main pedo-climatic conditions and farming systems in Europe, through 1) synthesis and meta-analysis of available literature and data; 2) targeted, novel measurements on key long-term experiments; and 3) simulation of long-term agro-ecological system responses to contrasting management options. Moreover, obtained data will be synthesized through a fuzzy-expert system which will allow for 4) evidence-based identification of optimal strategies for mitigation of trade-offs, and 5) effective stakeholders’ involvement.

By the end of M24 (January 2022) almost 80% of the project tasks have started, which is according to the project plan. More than 75% of the deliverables and milestones planned for the 1st project year have been achieved in time (see the table below). New deliverable dates have been planned for the delayed deliverables and the project is on track to achieve its goals.

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1 Consortium agreement	M13	Feb 2021	YES	M13	The consortium agreement of EJP Soil includes that of internal projects. A letter of commitment by Project Coordinator has been signed.
D1.2 Minutes of the kick-off meeting and project activity plan	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
D6.1 Detailed Plan for Communication and Dissemination	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
D3.1 Harmonized sampling and analysing protocol for field measurements of targeted trials	M15		NO		new date: M23 / Draft is prepared. Output from WP2.1 (knowledge gaps) will be considered for final refinement.
D1.3 Data management plan	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
D2.1 Report on knowledge gaps	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
D4.1 Template data output STICS, Armosa, PaSim (for WP2, WP3, WP5)	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
D6.2 A list of projects related soil, agriculture, environment, climate change and biodiversity.	M20		NO		new date: M26 / A list is in preparation
D6.3 Identification of stakeholders and platform constitution	M20		NO		new date: M23 / A list is drafted for Italy, Poland, Spain, Slovenia and Austria. To be checked and finalized.
M01 Consortium bodies and	M13	Feb 2021	YES	M13	

collaborative workspace operative					
M02 Kick-off meeting	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
M03 Dissemination Committee operative	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
M04 Connection with EJP SOIL WP9 established	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
M05 Template for database is available	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	
M06 Decision on input (selection field data) joint in silica experiments STICS, Armosa, PaSim (virtual meetings with WP2, WP3, WP5)	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	
M07 Fluent scenario of communication and dissemination among project partners, EJP WP9 and stakeholders	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	
M08 Questionnaire set-up in active interaction with WP2	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	
M09 Identification of knowledge gaps	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
M10 Detailed experimental plan for lab incubations and microbial analyses	M18	Jul 2021	NO		new date: M23 / Draft available, output from M09 will serve for final refinement
M11 Collection of soil cores for incubation activities	M20	Sep 2021	NO		new date: M23 / A subset of sites will be selected for incubation activities in winter 2021/22, based on M09 output

M12 Definition of the basic variables used as input to the fuzzy-expert system for trade-off analysis	M20	Sep 2021	YES	M20	
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CM8 – TRACE-Soils (project leader INIA, Spain)

Soil carbon sequestration in agroecosystems can promote soil quality and biodiversity, but can also come at a cost of increased nutrient losses and greenhouse gas emissions. Aiming to increase the predictability of such synergies and trade-offs, project is studying their underlying mechanisms by reviewing literature that quantifies them under different agricultural systems and management practices. Project intends to identify soil abiotic and biotic predictors of trade-off magnitudes, and test them in long-term experiments across a NE-SW pedoclimatic gradient in Europe. Modelling scenarios will be posed to scale-up trade-off analysis to the provincial level. Outputs of reviews, experiments and models will serve to propose a ranked list of climate-zone specific indicators and measures to assess and mitigate trade-offs.

Strategies to sequester carbon in agricultural soils are relevant to fight climate change. Increasing carbon content in soils promotes fertility and diversity, which is important to achieve sustainable agricultural systems. Paradoxically, under certain conditions, increasing carbon in soil could lead to larger greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient losses. TRACE-Soils will investigate when the pros or cons of carbon sequestration prevail and identify indicators and mitigation measurements to ensure that carbon sequestration is achieved without environmental costs.

The project has not had any deliverables planned for the 1st project year, but it has reached all the planned milestones, of which one was delayed by 3 months due to issues in soil sample collection. All the WPs have started their activities, except WP6 (Indicators), which is only planned to start on the 3rd project year. The project is on track to achieve its goals.

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M01 Project kick-off meeting	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	Kick-off meeting was carried out on March 4th, 2021
M02 WP1 Selection of studies completed	M15	Apr 2021	YES	M15	A total of 770 studies have been selected based on a systematic search and are currently being screened for subsequent database construction (details in Section 3.4, WP2)

M03 WP4 Collection and exchange of soil samples across long-term agricultural experiments completed	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M21	We delayed the collection of soil samples based on scientific and logistic reasons.
M04 WP4 Deployment of project online presence including webpage and social media accounts	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	

CM8 – INSURE (project leader LUKE, Finland)

Wet management with raised ground water table and flood-tolerant crops is an option to reduce peat decomposition and the related greenhouse gas emissions and water contamination from cultivated peatlands while still providing income for the farmers. However, there are sites with the risk of trade-offs like high methane or phosphorus emissions diminishing the environmental benefits. Measurable indicators used in the selection of sites would increase the success rate of rewetting and thus the acceptability of wet agricultural management of peat soils. Experimental work together with modelling and advanced analysis of peat composition in INSURE project aims at improved understanding of controls of element cycling in rewetted ecosystems and to finding robust indicators for the trade-offs of wet management.

By the end of M24 (January 2022) 85% of the project tasks have started, which is according to the project plan. There were no deliverables planned for the 1st project year, but the planned milestones have been achieved in time (see the table below). The project is well on track to achieve its goals.

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M01 WP3, Website created	M15	Apr 2021	YES	M15	
M02 WP5, Consortium agreement signed	M17	Jun 2021	YES	M17	
M03 WP5, Protocols for experimental work finalized	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	

M04 WP3, Session on Peatland Management at EGU 2021	M20	Sep 2021	YES	M20	
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MT1 – SensRes (project leader AU, Denmark)

Soil maps for large areas often fail to account for local variation in soil properties, due to their coarse resolutions. However, remote and proximal sensors can provide highly detailed soil information at a local level. Project therefore proposes a method to downscale large-extent soil maps using sensor data. Project will test the method for agricultural fields in six European countries, using proximal sensors, drone images and satellite images. The mapped soil properties will include soil organic carbon, soil texture and locally important soil properties. Project will test drone and satellite images of bare soils and vegetated fields, and we will test the effect of fusing data from different sensors. Project will also test the potential for using the downscaled soil maps in practical applications. SensRes aims to develop a general framework and to make the methods accessible to others.

By the end of M24 (January 2022) 75% of the project tasks have started, which is according to the project plan. The first two deliverables have been achieved in time, as well as majority of the milestones (see the table below). One milestone is delayed, but this is not expected to delay the overall progress of the project. The project is on track to achieve its goals.

Deliverable Milestone /	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1 WP0 First steering group meeting	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
D2 WP0 Kick-off meeting	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
M01 WP1, Online data repository ready	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
M02 WP1, All existing soil data collected	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	

M03 WP4, All satellite images collected and processed	M18	Jul 2021	NO	new date: M30 / We are collecting these data in collaboration with the STEROPES project, as both projects will need them, and there is an overlap between partners and study areas. Bare soil images have been collected for all study sites. The acquisition of vegetated satellite images may be delayed, as we aim to obtain satellite images coinciding with the UAV surveys in WP3. We do not expect this issue to delay the overall progress on the project.
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MT1 – STEROPES (project leader AgroParisTech, France)

Conventional high-detail soil maps are static and often based on obsolete data in relation to the time of use. STEROPES intends to overcome these limitations putting the use of satellite time series forward, to test their potential to predict cropland soil organic carbon content over various pedoclimatic conditions and cropping systems across Europe.

First, models will be constructed from the reflectance image spectra of optical satellite series, notably Sentinel-2 (ESA), based on a number of diversified areas for which soil organic carbon samples are already available. The second phase of the project will be dedicated to analysing the influence of various factors on SOC prediction performance: soil moisture, texture, green and dry vegetation due to management practices, salinity. Then, for the sites where satellite information may not enable to derive acceptable predictions, other ancillary data will be considered at a more detailed scale, using geophysical proxies to reduce the uncertainty associated with these predictions.

The overall aim is to test the potential to use satellite images to predict soil organic carbon content in agricultural soils across Europe. The project overall approach relies on the wide diversity of soil types and agricultural systems enabled by the STEROPES consortium: we are indeed 14 countries. The methodology starts from building spectral models, then focuses on the disturbing/influencing factors, and finally operates data synergy, and incorporates remote sensing into spatial models. We expect a number of relevant outcomes: first, a step-forward for digital soil mapping (DSM) of SOC content, a step-forward for the remote sensing of soils; second, enhancement of transnational collaboration and impact on approaches for carbon balance accounting; and finally, opening up of links with stakeholders for an enhanced use of remote sensing.

By the end of M24 (January 2022) more than 70% of the project tasks have started, which is according to the project plan. The first deliverable has been achieved in time, as well as the milestones (see the table below). The project is well on track to achieve its goals.

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D2 WP0 Kick-off meeting	M13	Mar 2021	YES	M13	Kick-off meeting was held remotely on 25 th March 2021.
M01 WP1 Database with sites with soil and satellite information for WP1	M13	Mar 2021	YES	M13	In progress. Database rather means “collection of data”, or collection of databases per partner.
M02 WP2, Database with sites with soil and satellite information for WP2	M16	Jun 2021	YES	M16	In progress. Database rather means “collection of data”, or collection of databases per partner.
M03 WP3, Database with sites with soil and satellite information for WP3	M16	Jun 2021	YES	M16	In progress. Database rather means “collection of data”, or collection of databases per partner.

SR5 – SCALE (project leader BAW, Austria)

A better understanding of sediment connectivity in agricultural landscapes can greatly improve the impact of mitigation strategies to reduce damages from soil erosion and provide better guidelines for decision makers and practitioners. SCALE is a consortium of 13 research institutes from 9 EU-countries that aims to improve the management of sediment connectivity in diverse agricultural landscapes. It composes i) current state-of-the-art of connectivity principles in modelling and legal standards, ii) data set harmonisation, iii) harmonisation of up- and downscaling methods, iv) evaluation of on- and off-site measures and connectivity elements in common modelling approaches, v) development of frameworks with mitigation measures and best management practices for stakeholders and vi) the communication of the project’s output. SCALE will significantly improve the harmonisation of data sets, observation and modelling techniques in connectivity research and bridge the gap between different spatial and administrative scales.

By the end of M24 (January 2022) a bit more than 40% of the project tasks have started, which is according to the project plan (WP3 and WP4 will start in the second project year). There were no planned deliverables for the first year, as 3 out of 4 planned milestones were reached in time (see the table below). The project is on track to achieve its goals.

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
WP6-D1 Website with project presentation, publication list, news feed and download area for modelling codes, road maps and guidelines	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	https://scale-ejpsoil.eu/
WP1-M1 : Workshop for conceptualising contents and structures of literature reviews	M12	Jan 2021	YES		
WP1-M2: Submission of modelling-based review	M17	Jun 2021	NO		new date: Dec 2021 / In order to get as much as survey replies as possible (and thus consider as much as EU member states and regions) we shifted the deadline for answering our survey, since we received some answers with quite a delay. Nevertheless, we received a sufficient number of answers from our survey, which have now been analysed. Hence, the delayed submission will absolutely not affect the progress of activities of the upcoming WPs and tasks.
WP2-M1: Workshop for definition of content, structure and platform of the common data base, as well as discussion on the further	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M21	new date: Oct 2021 / The workshop was re-scheduled in October 2021.

equipment of the research catchments					
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ES1/ES2 – SIREN (project leader WUR, Netherlands)

The SIREN project is making an inventory of indicator systems for assessing soil quality and ecosystem services, as currently used by Member States associated in the EJP SOIL and beyond. SIREN will identify and review the national frameworks and chains from soil properties via soil functions to soil ecosystem services and the indicators of soil quality state and functions plus their reference values across pedo-climatic conditions for the main agricultural production systems in the EU. Also, SIREN will identify if these have been translated into policy options and implementation, and into directions and guidance on land management. SIREN is particularly taking stock of the array of reference values for SOC, soil quality, soil biodiversity and degradation risk, the associated target values of indicators, and is identifying knowledge gaps and development needs.

The project was kicked-off during a video meeting between the Lead Partners on 4th of February 2021 (Milestone M01). Two major lines of work were set out, along Tasks 1 and 2:

1. Development of a draft conceptual framework to inform the structuring of the questionnaire for the stocktaking activity;
2. Development of the questionnaire, which addresses stocktakes ES (ecosystem services) 1 and ES2 at the same time.

SIREN is a one year stocktake project that has reached most of its milestones in time. The final report, deliverable 2, will be slightly delayed (M23 -> M25), although in the end this will increase the value of the report as discussions that are on-going with the European Environmental Agency will help to reach a common definition of key concepts related to soil health. The project SIREN has therefore applied for an extension of the project time for one month to finalize deliverable 2. The project is planned to end in M25, February 2022.

Deliverable Milestone	/	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M-01 Kick-off meeting, virtual		M13	Feb 2021	YES	M13	
M-02 ES framework drafted to support questionnaire development		M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
M-03 Questionnaire circulated among consortium Partners; webinar		M15	Apr 2021	YES	M15	

M04 Questionnaire feedback from consortium partners, start analysis	M17	Jun 2021	YES	M17	
M05 Contribution to EJP SOIL Newsletter	M18	Jul 2021	NO		The contribution to the EJP SOIL Newsletter is underway, but not completed.
M06 Go/no_go phase 2 stocktaking specific consortium partners	M19	Aug 2021	YES	M19	
M07 Go/no_go Framework adjustment following stocktake results	M20	Sep 2021	YES	M20	Revision is ongoing
M08 Compile 2nd phase feedback from consortium partners	M20	Sep 2021	NO		No compilation of 2nd feedback needed, as we did not have a second phase in the stocktake activity.
M09 Input draft results for EJP SOIL Roadmap updating	M20	Sep 2021	YES	M20	
D-1 Metadata submitted for archiving by EJP SOIL WP6	M22	Nov 2021			In collaboration with EJP SOIL WP6
D-2 Final Report	M23	Dec 2021	NO	M25	SIREN is discussing with the European Environmental Agency on a common definition of key concepts related to soil health, in order to come out with a common understanding.

FS2/MT4 - i-SOMPE (project leader CRAW, Belgium)

Innovative soil management practices (SMP) and agricultural systems are promoted to enhance ecosystem services in order to minimise soil threats and sustain agriculture in a climate change context. A comprehensive stocktake of SMPs and their ability to succeed on multiple goals, agricultural

production, ecosystem services, biogeochemical cycles, is missing. By using a surveying approach, i-SoMPE will aim to documents these innovative farming practice. The data gathered will be synthesized considering technical and ecological constrains and socio-economic barriers. Context-specific thematic maps will be provided to guide policy makers to the most efficient innovative SMPs as climate-smart sustainable tools.

Project i-SoMPE is a one year stocktake project that has asked for extension due to delays in the large surveys. They have reached most of their milestones in time and therefore an extension of two months of the project time was granted and i-SoMPE will deliver their final report in M26.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
WP1-D2 Framework to match SMP with environmental zones	M20	Sep 2021	YES	M21	The Framework is already finished, only the report need to be polished and submitted.
WP4-D3 Data base of the SMP inventory, GIS and data exploration application	M23	Dec 2021			
WP4-D4 Final report (including inventory of descriptive sheets of practices)	M24	Jan 2022	NO	M26	
WP5-D5 Report of the annual meeting	M24	Jan 2022			
WP1-MS2 Preliminary framework to match SMP with environmental zones	M15	Apr 2021	YES	M15	
WP1-MS3 Interview grid and online tool for collecting data, survey I	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	
WP1-MS8 Interview grid and online tool for collecting data, survey II	M20	Sep 2021	YES	M21	Slightly delayed, we required some supplementary week to identify what kind of data could be the most relevant for completing the first survey.

WP2-MS4 Online informational meeting & training course on surveys	M17	Jun 2021	YES	M17	
WP3-M5 List of proposed environmental zone, interviewees and practices	M17	Jun 2021	YES	M17	
WP3-MS6 Closing of survey I	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M19	Report delayed due to summer break in Europe.
WP3-MS9 Closing of survey II	M21	Oct 2021	NO		The survey II is planned to end in M24 due to large workload and scheduling issues because of the winter break.
WP4-MS7 Application for visualizing and exploring data from surveys	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
WP5-MS10 Final meeting	M24	Jan 2022			

CA1 – CLIMASOMA (project leader ILVO, Belgium)

CLIMASOMA will directly contribute to an alignment of research strategies connecting agricultural management, soil quality and climate adaptation potential through its summary of the literature, its meta-analysis and its identification of knowledge gaps. First results of the EJP SOIL CLIMASOMA confirm that maintaining a ‘continuous living cover’ matters to foster the water regulatory function of soils. Agricultural management practices and cropping systems determine whether soil can help us adapt to the changing climate with increased occurrence of climatic extremes such as drought or peak rainfall events. Nevertheless, context is key to understand the interplay between soils, their environment and human interventions. Machine learning offers a lot of potential to highlight those context-specific interactions, but cannot perform better than the databases at hand to train the algorithms. There is a need to invest in soil databases with sufficient metadata on management and environmental factors.

CLIMASOMA is a one-year project but due to the latest COVID-19 wave in Europe, the project coordination had to cancel the physical final consortium meeting in Switzerland Mid January. Since the project participants have not been able to meet physically and to further strengthen interactions between different work packages and persons in the consortium, the project was extended by 2 months to end on M26, March 2022. CLIMASOMA will deliver the final report in M24 and the delay will concern the final meeting and the finalisation of our policy brief and infographic (all in M26).

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1 WP1 Project and database network map	M13	Feb 2021	YES	M22	The presentation of the deliverable was behind the schedule. All planned activities were completed except the visualization of the network map online. Contact was sought with EJP SOIL WP9 (Dissemination and outreach) to find a solution to put the network map online for interactive use.
D1-WP6.D1 Project handbook	M13	Feb 2021	YES		During the kickoff meeting, the topics of the project handbook were discussed. The minutes serve as handbook.
D2-WP1.D2 Manual explaining methodology behind network map	M14	Mar 2021	YES		
D1.3 WP1 Chapter: Inventory of motivations and barriers for adopting recommended measures for soil related climate adaptation by farmers	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M20	
D1.4 WP1 Chapter: Inventory of relevant policy packages and strategies that affect soil related climate adaptation by farmers	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M20	

D1.5 WP1 Policy brief describing action perspectives for farmers, policy makers, extension services and researchers to stimulate transition to soil related climate adaptation practices	M19	Aug 2021	NO		After completion of all the chapters, the policy brief will be extracted from them. We are waiting for all the chapters to be written, so we can integrate everything at best in the policy brief. This will be more meaningful than produce a policy brief based on just two chapters.
D6.2 WP6 Minutes of official meetings	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	
D6.2 WP6 Minutes of official meetings	M15 M18 M21	Apr 2021 Jul 2021 Oct 2021	YES	M15 M18 M21	
D2-WP2.D2 CLIMASOMA database in BonaRes data portal	M23	Dec 2021			
D1-WP3.D1 Chapter: soil and crop management for climate adaptation through soil hydrological and biological functioning	M23	Dec 2021			
D2-WP3.D2 Chapter: soil management and cropping systems for climate adaptation: impact of changing climatic drivers (P, T, pCO₂)	M23	Dec 2021			

D3-WP3.D3 Chapter: overview of soil-crop models: potential and limitations of existing approaches to assess crop production under climate change and options for improvements	M23	Dec 2021			
D1-WP4.D1 Chapter: quantitative relationships on soil management and crop management	M23	Dec 2021			
D2-WP4.D2 Chapter: potential of machine learning to uncover context-specific relationships	M23	Dec 2021			
D1-WP5.D1 Synthesis report	M23	Dec 2021			
D2-WP5.D2 Policy brief on soil management and cropping systems for climate adaptation	M23	Dec 2021			
D3-WP5.D3 Infographic	M23	Dec 2021			
M1 WP1 Network map available for project partners	M13	Feb 2021	YES	M13	

M2 WP1 Network map available for public	M14	Mar 2021	YES	M14	
M3 WP1 Inventory of motivations and barriers for adopting recommended measures for soil-related climate adaptation by farmers	M17	Jun 2021	YES	M17	
M3 WP2 50 Papers entered in BonaRes knowledge library	M16	May 2021	YES	M20	The 29 papers identified in WP3 task 1 have been entered into the Bonares library. Since task 2 needed to be finished first, the papers used for this analysis were entered in Bonares when the search was finalized (M20).
M4 WP2 Database selected	M16	May 2021	YES	M16	
M13 WP5 Halfway internal EJP soil digital seminar organized	M18	Jul 2021	YES	M18	We use the EJP SOIL webinar format to organise our halfway seminar. >200 subscriptions, 115 attendees the day itself.
M5 WP2 Database available	M19	Aug 2021	YES	M19	
M7 WP3 All relevant papers added to KLIB and analyzed	M19	Aug 2021	YES	M20	
M9 WP4 Statistical description and visualization of the data completed	M21	Oct 2021	YES	M21	

M10 WP4 Data diagnostics completed (e.g. estimation of publication bias)	M21	Oct 2021	YES	M21	
M11 WP4 Data interpretation completed	M22	Nov 2021			
M12 WP4 Jupyter notebooks to document data processing and meta-analysis completed	M23	Dec 2021			
M14 WP5 First draft of report shared with project partners	M22	Nov 2021			
M15 WP5 Final CA1 EJP soil seminar organized (physical or digital) if feasible together with the EJP Soil science days.	M23	Dec 2021			

2.2. EJP SOIL 2nd internal call projects

For the second call, 9 topics for medium-large research projects were launched. Two topics regarded to Climate Change Mitigation (CM1, CM5), one to Climate change adaptation and Sustainable production (CA4/SP3), two more topics for Sustainable production (SP1, SP2), one for Harmonizing soil information (DATA1), two for Sustainable environment indicators (SE2/INDICATORS 1 and SE4/INDICATORS 2), and one related to science policy interface and Ecosystem services (POL2/ES7).

Eleven proposals were submitted, 2 for CM1 and CM5, and one for each of the remaining topics. After the evaluation process, one (CA4/SP3) was rejected because the low score. The total number of approved proposals was 10. The average number of partners by project was 14 (range 9 - 25 depending on the type). Regarding geographical distribution, 40% of the project proposals were submitted by coordinators from Northern Europe (2 from Denmark and 2 from Sweden), 40% by coordinators from Central and West Europe (3 from France, 1 from Austria) and 20% (2) from Southern Europe (Italy) but none of the submitted project proposals was coordinated by an EJP SOIL member from East and Southeast Europe.

The duration was 3 years for all the projects. The grant size was approximately 2 M€ for each project with the exception of the topic SE2/INDICATORS 1, which received almost 5M€, this project (SERENA) is a large project with 25 partners involved. This information is detailed in D3.5 “List of selected proposals of 2nd internal call”.

CM1 - MIXROOT-C (project leader INRAE, France)

MIXROOT-C project aims to measure in situ root carbon (C) production and to propose root traits related to soil organic C storage in topsoil and subsoil in the context of diversified agrosystems in Europe (e.g. intercropping, grasslands, and agroforestry). The project accounts for the interactions between climate, soil type, above- and belowground plant compartments, plant species and soil C. In order to provide a reliable assessment of belowground C inputs of mixed species systems across Europe and to assess the related co-benefits and trade-offs associated to an increase in root productivity, MIXROOT-C will use complementary approaches, including literature reviewing, collection of existing and new data from long-term field experiments, and process-based modelling.

Deliverable / Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M3.1 Glossary of common vocabulary, units and definitions	M23	Dec 2021			

CM1 - MaxRoot-C (project leader BOKU, Austria)

To reduce the effect of climate change on food security, carbon farming is indispensable. Mobilizing crop producers to support this transformation requires promotion of cropping systems with equivalent profitability, but higher soil C sequestration. The most viable yet neglected option is through increased and deeper roots of main and cover crops. MaxRoot-C will pioneer assessment methods closing this knowledge gap by providing robust hard data on the root C inputs of main crop varieties and different

cover crops across the EU, to determine main drivers and model the C sequestering potential therein. It will provide policy relevant data on which to base future CAP instruments and contribute to the development of future carbon sequestration standards for the EU approved seed lists.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP month	Delivery, SOIL Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1 Internal management structure and communication strategy implemented.	M23	Dec 2021			
M2.1 Crops, genotypes and sites are selected	M24	Jan 2022			
M3.1 Information for meta-analysis compiled	M24	Jan 2022			

CM5 – AGROECOseqC (project leader CREA, Italy)

Soil fauna and microbial communities drive key ecosystem functions, such as nutrient supply to primary production and SOC accumulation. However, plant diversity shapes soil biota composition and activity via rhizodeposition and N-P uptake, microbial symbioses, and trophic cascades. In EU experimental sites network, the project will study how agroecological intensification of cropping systems (e.g. introduction of plant services) can allow better regulation of degradation/resynthesis of soil organic matter and nutrient cycling by the plant-soil system. Advantages and disadvantages of such agroecological systems will be compared to less conservative ones for plant-soil fauna-microbial functional diversity, biomass production, N-leaching, soil C-stable pools, GHG emission and C sequestration.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP month	Delivery, SOIL Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1.1 Protocols for sampling and analysis for AGROECOseqC mandatory parameters	M24	Jan 2022			
D2.1.1 Protocol for Phytosociological surveys	M24	Jan 2022			
D2.2.1 Protocol for plantmycorrhizal	M24	Jan 2022			

colonization intensity					
D2.2.2 Protocol for SEM analysis of mycorrhizal mycelial network	M24	Jan 2022			
D.2.3 Protocol for plantsampling, nutrient content analysis and PDB screening	M24	Jan 2022			
D3.1.1 Protocols for soil microfauna sampling	M24	Jan 2022			
D3.2.1 Protocols for soil mesofauna sampling	M24	Jan 2022			
D3.3.1 Protocols for soil macrofauna sampling	M24	Jan 2022			
D6.1.1 Protocols for C-pools and soil aggregates analysis	M24	Jan 2022			
D6.1.2 Protocols for C/N semi-quantitative analysis by SEM-EDS	M24	Jan 2022			
D8.1 Project communication plan	M24	Jan 2022			
M1.1.1 Recruitment of AGROECOseqC Advisory board	M22	Nov 2021			
M1.3.1 AGROECOseqC kick-off meeting	M23	Dec 2021			
M1.1.2 State of art of experimental sites and potential interconnection with other EJP SOIL projects	M24	Jan 2022			
M1.1.3 Selection of experimental sites	M24	Jan 2022			

and agricultural practices					
M1.2.1 AGROECOseqC mandatory/optional parameters (dataset)	M24	Jan 2022			
M5.1.1 Definition of a protocol applicable to all sites	M24	Jan 2022			
M5.3.1 Protocol of ¹³Cpulse labelling	M24	Jan 2022			

CM5 - EnergyLink (project leader SLU, Sweden)

Crop diversification is a potentially attractive agricultural practice for enhancing organic C storage in soils. The aim of EnergyLink is to understand the link between crop diversity and the processing of organic C by the soil microbiome across a pan-European pedo-climatic gradient. The central hypothesis is that greater crop diversity results in more efficient microbial use of C, thus enhancing the potential of soils to store C. The underlying mechanisms will be elucidated by combining molecular level methods in a bioenergetics framework. Data will inform models describing the turnover of soil organic matter and implement future climate scenarios. The project will provide policy relevant data on which to base future CAP instruments and contribute to the development of carbon farming.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1 Consortium agreement	M22	Nov 2021			
D1.2 Data Management plan	M24	Jan 2022			
D1.3 Risk and quality management plan	M24	Jan 2022			
M1.1 Consortium Agreement	M23	Dec 2021			
M1.2 Kick-off meeting	M24/25	Jan / Feb 2022			

M2.1 Selected field sites within EnergyLink	M23	Dec 2021			
M2.2 Standard Operation Procedures (SOP)	M23	Dec 2021			
M2.3 Harmonization EJP SOIL projects	M24	Jan 2022			

SP1 - SoilCompaC (project leader AU, Denmark)

Soil compaction is a major threat to soil productivity and ecological and hydrological soil functioning. Although adverse impacts of compaction on soil properties and functions are relatively well documented, estimates of the extent and severity of compaction in Europe remain elusive, we have limited knowledge on how compaction changes the carbon cycle, and we lack information on compaction risks for different pedo-climatic zones and cropping systems in Europe and how the risks evolve due to climate change. SoilCompaC directly addresses these knowledge gaps. SoilCompaC will quantify interactions between soil compaction and climate, and present information on how to assess, detect, recover and minimize soil compaction, thereby providing a basis for sustainable soil management in Europe.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.5 Compilation of literature and data from current experiments	M22	Nov 2021			
D4.1 Project plan	M24	Jan 2022			
M4.1 Kick off plenary meeting	M22	Nov 2021			

SP2 - EOM4SOIL (project leader INRAE, France)

EOM4SOIL aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Representative farming systems in Europe (arable crops and vineyards) are selected, taking into account the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. The net budget of soil C storage and greenhouse gas emission including the pre-process step and field application, is assessed as well as the multiple effects of EOM application on soils including contaminants are quantified. Innovative pre-processing are recommended to improve C budget and soil health. The best management practices are defined from scenarios of use assessed with a multicriteria simulation tool, parameterized from long-term experiments.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D7.1.1 Kick-off meeting report	M23	Dec 2021			
M1.1 Data base construction to be filled with each EOM	M24	Jan 2022			
M 7.1.1 Kick-off meeting	M22	Nov 2021			
M 7.2.1 Webinar of presentation	M24	Jan 2022			

DATA1 - ProbeField (project leader SLU, Sweden)

Quick and simple soil analyses directly in the field through proximal sensing has the potential to substantially gear up the number of samples analysed. With focus on visible and near infrared spectroscopy (Vis-NIRS) ProbeField will work to make this happen. The Vis-NIR technique has many advantages required for field analyses of soil properties. There are, however, drawbacks to be overcome. In contrast to spectroscopy in the lab on prepared samples, variable moisture and structure in the field will hamper reliability of analyses. ProbeField will test and suggest physical and mathematical procedure to manage these problems. A wide range of soil properties will be analysed and 3D mapping will be performed to estimate for example carbon stocks. A best practice protocol will be produced.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M1.4 Communication through websites and social media	M24	Jan 2022			
M2.1 Collection of relevant literature	M24	Jan 2022			
M3.1 Literature review	M24	Jan 2022			

SE2/IND1 - SERENA (project leader INRAE, France)

The ongoing shift from a merely productive conception of soils towards a more integrative vision of multifunctional soil quality requires a shared analysis of concepts and definitions, and the integration of innovative assessment tools into land planning and soil policies at different scales. SERENA intends to meet these requirements by putting relevant stakeholders at the core of the project, and by providing co-developed indicators and related interpretation values, able to report both on soil degradation and soil-based ecosystem services. Using relevant information on soil quality and soil health, SERENA will jointly evaluate bundles of soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats, and model their evolution depending on climate and management, from the local to the European scales. The SERENA project has started well with a kick-off meeting held on 13th and 14th of December 2021. In maximum the meeting had 82 participants. During the meeting the overall project structure was presented as well as interdependencies among and within the WPs were identified, as well as connections to other EJP SOIL WPs and projects.

Deliverable Milestone	/	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M3.1 Draft template for collecting information on existing experiences on soil functions, threats and soil-based ecosystem services		M23	Dec 2021			
M6.1 Kick-off meeting		M23	Dec 2021	YES	M23	

SE4/IND2 - MINOTAUR (project leader CREA, Italy)

The current status and trends in soil biodiversity across Europe are poorly known, and adequate taxonomical and functional indicators are needed to evaluate the vulnerability of soils to climate change. MINOTAUR aims to provide models, maps and policy-relevant indicators with validated reference values for monitoring soil biodiversity and associated functions. Moreover, it will aim to understand how agricultural practices can contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation at regional and national levels across the EU. The project will collaborate with relevant EU research projects, international soil biodiversity networks and programs to harmonize and integrate soil biodiversity data and contribute to support long-term harmonized EU soil information and international reporting. The MINOTAUR project has started well with a kick-off meeting held on 26th and 27th of January 2022.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
D1.1 Consortium agreement	M23	Dec 2021			
D1.2 Minutes of the kick-off meeting	M24	Jan 2022			
MS1.1 Collaborative workspace	M23	Dec 2021			
MS1.2 Kickoff meeting	M24	Jan 2022			

POL2/ES7 - Road4Schemes (project leader AU, Denmark)

Carbon farming has gained prominence as a mitigation option to reach targets set in the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal. To achieve this, integrating research into policy design and implementation, ensuring mutual benefits for stakeholders, soils and society is helpful. Road4Schemes will (1) assess the strengths and weaknesses of existing and planned schemes for carbon farming and additional Ecosystem Service (ESS) payments, including respective tools for monitoring, reporting and verification; (2) assess stakeholders' perceptions and preferences with respect to strategies for scheme design and policy drivers and barriers; and (3) deliver a roadmap for developing and implementing contextually sensitive result-based schemes for carbon farming and additional ESS payments.

Deliverable Milestone	Delivery, EJP SOIL month	Delivery, Calendar month	Delivered (YES/NO)	Actual date of delivery	In case of delay justify reasons and corrective measures
M1.1 Meeting with project management team	M22	Nov 2021			

